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Factors associated with self mutilation

Ali Al-Ubadi Psychiatrist
Al- Yarmook teaching hospital
Baghdad, Iraq

Ghazi Aboud Psychiatrist
Al- Rashad Hospital
Baghdad, Iraq.
E-mail:ghazi957@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: Self-mutilation is deliberate self-harm without the intent of death. The reported motivations for self-mutilation include punishment, tension reduction and mood improvement.

Aim of study: To study the psychological, educational, criminal & motivational factors associated with self inflicted wounds.

Patients and method: 24 male patients with self harm observed at Al-Rasheed hospital and Al-Yarmook teaching hospital during the period between June 2002 –March 2003 were enrolled in this study and interviewed by the authors. Evaluation included IQ assessment (Raven) and EEG recording.

Results: Tension reduction was the main motivational factor associated with self-cutting or burning. EEG study was normal in 21 patients, while I.Q ranged between (60 –110).14 patients (58%). All of them injured their upper limbs and 21 patients (88%) had been injured by sharp instrument.

The self-mutilator reports a range of motivations, including self-punishment, tension reduction, improvement in mood, and distraction from intolerable

were habituated on hallucinogens and 10 patients (42%) did the act due to internal tension.

Conclusion: Tension reduction was the main motivational factor associated with self-cutting or burning. All of mutilations were involved upper limbs and personality disorders were a common cause in the mutilators.

Key words: self mutilation motivational Factors

Introduction

Self-mutilation is deliberate self harm with out the intent of death [1].The most usual forms are cutting and burning. [2,3].Age at onset typically is between 14 – 24 years[4, 5].Self-mutilation is characterized typically by a sense of rising tension before the act and preoccupation with strong and persistent urges to hurt oneself [6]. At some point, the urge becomes overwhelming, the individual is no longer able or willing to resist, and he then engages in self-mutilation.

affects [2, 3]. Following the act, the individual usually reports feeling better and relieved [2, 3, 7, 8]. It has been speculated that self-mutilating behaviour

serves a coping function that is activated by an increase in emotional arousal [9,10]. Observations in non-human mammals have shown that self-mutilating behaviours may emerge as a consequence of deprived rearing conditions[11,12]. Thus, self-mutilating behaviour may be regarded as an unusual, but effective coping strategy for the self-regulation of hyper arousal and/or dissociative states and for regaining control over an otherwise uncontrollable stress response[13]. Linehan postulated that all deliberate self-harm ought to be considered on a continuum of lethality, regardless of the intention to die[14]. The most commonly used object is a knife, razor, glass piece, scissors, and ice pick are the other objects used[15]. Skin cutting appears to be the most common form of self-harm, occurring in at least 70% of individuals who harm themselves [4, 5,16,17, 18], and between 15% and 35% burn their skin [4, 5, 17, 18]. Self-inflicted wound commonly seen over the wrist, elbow, neck and the trunk [19]. Self-inflicted abdominal stab wounds usually cause non-lethal injuries but sometime result in significant injuries [15]. Psychotic and non-psychotic genital self-mutilation is well recognized in males but not in females [20]. The borderline personality has been described as not genuinely suicidal or life-threatening but primarily attention-seeking behaviour and manipulative[21]. The self-mutilating patients reported significantly greater frequency of physical punishment during

childhood but did not report more frequent sexual abuse [22].

Patients and Methods

24 patients (outpatients and inpatients) with self-mutilation were observed in Al-Rasheed Military hospital and Al-Yarmook teaching hospital during the period from June 2002 to March 2003. Their ages ranged from 18 to 33, 15 patients (62%) their ages ranged between 20 and 30 years, 6 patients (25%) their ages between 18-20 years and, 3 patients (13%) their ages ranged between 30-33 years. All of them were males. All the patients were interviewed by authors (psychiatrist) and clinically assessed; in addition to that EEG and I.Q (Raven) had been done.

Results

Past history: 2 patients (8 %) have sexual abuse at childhood 2 patients (8%) got closed head injury

Marital state (Figure-1): 17 patients (71%) were single, and 2 patients (8%) were married while 5 patients (21%) were divorced.

Scholastic Achievement (figure-2): 10 patients (42%) reached elementary school, 7 Patients (29%), who reached intermediate school, 2 (8%) Patients reached secondary school 5 patients (21%) were illiterate.

Criminal history figure (3).

Intelligence Quotient (IQ): IQ ranged between 60 -110 .Only one patients is subnormal as in table (1).

I.Q level	No. of patients	Percentage %
-7060	1	4
70-90	14	58
90 -110	9	38

Types of mutilation (figure 4).

Substance abuse

Five patients (21%) have history of alcohol consumption, while 14 of them (58%) were habituated on hallucinogens especially artane (benzhixol), including one patient Committed homicide

Site of self-harm: An affected bodily part of mutilation is shown in table 2.

Parts of body	No. of patients	Percentage %
upper limb ,face, neck ,chest, abdomen	2	8
upper limb,neck,chest, abdomen	5	21
upper limb,chest,abdomen	9	38
Upper limb	7	29
Upper limb, neck, chest ,abdomen ,thigh, sexual organs	1	4

Motivation of act as shown in table 3.

motives	No. of patients	Percentage %
Aggression toward the self	7	29
Internal tension	10	42
Aggression toward others	4	17
Asking for help	1	4
None	2	8

Psychiatric diagnosis as shown in table 4.

Diagnosis	No. of patients	Percentage %
Acute psychosis	2	8
Psychosis &M.R	1	4
Borderline personality	2	8
Other personality disorder	15	63
Psychopathic personality	4	17

EEG was normal in 21 patients (88%) A generalized slow wave activity was present in one patient with mental retardation EEG was abnormal in 2 patients (8%) for whom C.T scan was done and it was normal.

Discussion

The finding that only male patients with self-mutilation was observed was unexpected, as it is often reported that self-harm is more common in women than men or difference in the prevalence for men and women [16, 18,23,24 25,26].In this community social causes could have forbidden females from coming to the hospital .

The patients aged from 18 – 33, but 62% of the patients aged 20 to 30 years. Judith Horrocks etal [27] reported slightly older than that reported elsewhere [28, 29].

Cutting the skin by sharp instrument were more common (88%) than other type and this was higher than the reported in other studies[4,5,16,17,18].While 8% of patients harm themselves by burning and this was less than the reported by other studies[4,5,17,18].As in previous studies the upper limb was the most common part of the body injured [29]. The multiple cutting was 66.5% in

Judith Horrocks study [27] while in our study was 71%.

Internal tension is the common motive (42%) for inducing self-mutilation [6]. and there is physiological evidence that self-harmers experience a reduction in tension after an episode of self-harm [2, 3, 7, 8, 16]

Self-mutilators have higher rates of personality disorder (88%),including borderline personality(8%),psychopathic personality (16%) and other personality disorder(62%).These findings are consistent with other studies([17,30].

Habituation on hallucinogens was present in (58%) and alcohol consumption in (21%) and these results were not differ from several studies which have reported association between substance abuse and deliberate self-harm [17, 31, 32]. These drugs decrease the pain and cause a state of dissociation explaining this association. Tantam and Whittaker reported that many patients have a history of sexual abuse [33], but in this study only 8% have such history. 58% had been in trouble with the police and this may be due to a lot of failure in school, military service and employment.

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